

Knowledge Regarding Sexually Transmitted Disease (STD's) among B.Sc. Nursing First Year Students

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ABSTRACT

Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) are the infections which are mainly transmitted through sexual intercourse. The common STIs which we come across in daily practice are gonorrhoea, cancrroids, syphilis, and Chlamydia infections which can be cured and others such as HIV, genital herpes, HPV, and hepatitis B infection which cannot be cured but can be modified with the available treatments. Sexually transmitted diseases are a major health problem affecting mostly young people, not only in developing, but also in developed countries. It is the major health problem in developing and developed countries. They cause serious health economic and social consequences. The main aim of the study is to assess the knowledge regarding sexually transmitted disease among B.Sc. nursing first year students. A quantitative descriptive survey study was conducted to assess the knowledge regarding STD's and to find the association between knowledge score with selected demographic variable. Total 100 study participants were selected by purposive sampling technique from B.Sc. nursing first year, Faculty of Nursing, SGT University, Gurugram, Haryana. Data revealed most of the study participants 96% had good knowledge regarding sexually transmitted disease and 4% study participants had average knowledge regarding sexually transmitted disease. It was concluded that B.Sc. nursing first year students had good knowledge regarding sexually transmitted disease.

KEYWORDS: Knowledge, Sexually transmitted disease, B.Sc. nursing students

I. INTRODUCTION

Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) are the infections which are mainly transmitted through sexual intercourse. The common STIs which we come across in daily practice are gonorrhoea, cancrroids, syphilis, and Chlamydia infections which can be cured and others such as HIV, genital herpes, HPV, and hepatitis B infection which cannot be cured but can be modified with the available treatments.

Young individuals in the age group of 16–24 years are considered to be at more risk for STIs compared to older adults. The World Health Organization estimates that 20% of persons living with HIV/AIDS are in their 20s and one out of twenty adolescents contract an STI each year.

Each year, there are an estimated 376 million new infections with 1 of 4 STIs: Chlamydia, gonorrhoea, syphilis and trichomoniasis. More than 500 million people are estimated to have genital infection with herpes simplex. More than 290 million women have a human papillomavirus (HPV)

1.1. Need of the study:-

India having a large population with low literacy levels leading to a low level of awareness of HIV/AIDS. The disease is posing an alarming threat on the public health scenario, at the same time discussing sex has been a taboo in the Indian societal set up. Adolescence is so in myths and

misconceptions about sexual health and sexuality with the influence of media and the breakdown of traditional family structures, sexual behavior among adolescents is in flux.

STIs have a profound impact on sexual and reproductive health worldwide. In 2016, WHO estimated 376 million new infections with 1 of 4 STIs: Chlamydia (127 million), Gonorrhoea (87 million), Syphilis (6.3 million), Trichomoniasis (156 million).

About 1.1 billion people had STIs other than HIV/AIDS. About 500 million were infected with either syphilis, gonorrhoea, Chlamydia or Trichomoniasis. STIs other than HIV resulted in 108,000 deaths in 2015.

1.2. Statement of the problem:-

A descriptive study to assess the knowledge regarding STDs among B.Sc. nursing first year students of selected collage of nursing, Gurugram, Haryana

1.3. Objectives:-

- To assess the knowledge regarding STD's among B.Sc. nursing first year students.
- To find the association between knowledge score with selected demographic variable of B.Sc. nursing first year students.

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1.4. Assumptions:-

- B.Sc. nursing first year students will have some knowledge regarding STD's
- Sample will be true representation of population.

1.5. Delimitation:-

- Only one setting
- Non standardized instruments
- Study was delimited to only B.Sc. nursing first year students of selected college of Gurugram, Haryana.

II. METHODOLOGY

The research design used in this study was non experimental descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted at Faculty of Nursing, SGT University, Gurugram,

Haryana. The sample was 100 B.Sc. nursing first year students were selected by using purposive sampling technique. The tool used for the study was self structured knowledge questionnaire. Section A description of demographic characteristics of the study participants (demographic data such as gender, age, educational status, residential area, do you know anything about STD and source of information) Section B self structured knowledge questionnaire related to STD. The content validity of tools was done by submitting the tools to seven experts from different nursing departments to seek their opinion and suggestions regarding the items in tools. The reliability of knowledge questionnaire was established by spit half method followed by Karl person correlation ($r=0.99$)

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1. Related to demographic variable of B.Sc. nursing first year students.

N=100

S. No	Socio demographic variables	Opts	Frequency(f)	Percentage(%)
1.	Gender	Male	33	33%
		Female	67	67%
2.	Age in years	17-18 years	41	41%
		19-20 years	47	47%
		20 year above	12	12%
3.	Previous knowledge about STD	Yes	96	96%
		No	4	4%
4.	Source of information	Tv	16	16%
		Radio	1	1%
		Newspaper	7	7%
		Friends/colleagues	30	30%
		Health Care Professionals	18	18%
		Others	28	28%

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE NO 3.1

Demographic variable revealed that that 67% of subjects were female. 47% of subjects were in 19-20 years of age group. 96% of students having previous knowledge regarding STDs. 30% of subjects having knowledge regarding STD from their colleague/friends.

3.2. Frequency and Percentage of knowledge score about the STDs.

Level of knowledge	Scores range	Frequency {f}	Percentage{%
Good knowledge	21-30	96	96%
Average knowledge	11-20	4	4%
Poor knowledge	0-10	0	0%

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE NO 3.2

Data revealed that most 96% of study participants had good knowledge regarding sexually transmitted disease and 4% of study participants had average knowledge regarding sexually transmitted disease.

3.3. Mean, Median and Standard Deviation of knowledge score about the STDs.

Table 3:- Mean, Median and Standard Deviation of knowledge score about the STDs.

N=100

Descriptive statistics	Mean	Median	Standard deviation	Maximum	Minimum	Range	Mean%
Knowledge score	23.90	2	1.80	28	20	8	79.67

3.4. Related to association between knowledge score with selected demographic variables of B.Sc. nursing first year students

Variables	Opts	Good	Average	Poor	Chi Test	P Value	Df	Table Value	Level of significance
Gender	Male	33	0		2.052	0.152	1	3.841	NS
	Female	63	4						
Age in Years	17-18 years	37	4		5.996	0.050	2	5.991	S
	19-20 years	47	0						
	20 year above	12	0						
Previous knowledge about STD	Yes	92	4		0.174	0.677	1	3.841	NS
	No	40	0						
Source of Information	TV	15	1		2.049	0.842	5	11.070	NS
	Radio	1	0						
	Newspaper	7	0						
	Friends/Colleagues	29	1						
	Health Care Professionals	18	0						
	Others	26	2						

NS= Not significant, S= Significant

DESCRIPTION OF TBLE NO 3.4

This table shows that there is no significant association between knowledge score with selected demographic variable except age.

IV. NURSING IMPLICATIONS

Nursing education-The study has an important implication in nursing education and other fields. Nursing students can give teaching program regarding STDs.

Nursing practice-Nurses are the backbone of health care set up of any country. The nursing knowledge has gone many evolutions in recent past. The expanded role of professional nurse emphasizes the implication which involves primitive, preventive, curative and rehabilitative aspects.

Nursing Research-A very few interventional studies have been conducted regarding STDs.

- Knowledge and practice study can be conducted on STDs.
- Comparative study can be conducted in B.Sc. nursing 1st year students of selected college of nursing Gurugram, Haryana.

V. CONCLUSION

Study concluded that B.Sc. nursing first year students have good knowledge regarding sexually transmitted disease and only few 4% of study participants have average knowledge regarding sexually transmitted disease.

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Gratitude can never be expressed in words but this is only deep perception that the words to flow from one's inner heart.

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